

The problem of pronouncing the English *th* sounds /θ/ and /ð/ of Vietnamese learners

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Abstract

This article investigates the problem that EFL learners in Vietnam commonly come across issues when pronouncing the *th* sounds /θ/ and /ð/ in English. It is reported that they frequently substitutes /t^h/ for the voiceless sound /θ/ and /d/ for the voiced sound /ð/. The analysis indicates that the influence of first language (L1), the struggle in using tongue and teeth, and the proficiency level of Vietnamese learners of English are considered as the main factors causing the abovementioned problematic pronunciation. To help students overcome their difficulties, comprehensively instructing the way to pronounce /θ/ and /ð/ sounds correctly, using minimal pairs with numerous examples, and creating a inspired learning environment for the students to practice pronunciation are recommended.

Keywords: pronunciation, pronouncing, th sounds, /θ/, /ð/, difficulties, errors

1. INTRODUCTION

A deliberation of pronunciation errors seems to be crucial in order to enhance a deep understanding of how language learners learn phonetic knowledge. One important aspect of second language (L2) pronunciation needing to be paid attention to is the perception of non-L1 speech sounds (Munro, 2018).

Specifically, some speech sounds in English are not found in Vietnamese dialects, such as voiceless *th* sound /θ/ (as in *thank* /θæŋk/ or *math* /mæθ/) and voiced *th* sound /ð/ (as in *these* /ði:z/ or *mother* /'mʌðər/). Because the *th* sounds /θ/ and /ð/ in English language are not existent in Vietnamese language, many EFL learners in Vietnam feel difficult to appropriately pronounce these sounds in English. From personal teaching experience, it is noticed that Vietnamese learners of English usually substitutes /t^h/ for /θ/ and /d/ for /ð/.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Pronunciation problems and reasons explaining for the difficulties may be found in a wide variety of research papers. Munro (2018) believes that the sound system of first language (L1) create a considerable impact on how L2 pronunciation is acquired by language learners. Based on the contrastive analysis hypothesis, “the structural differences between L1 and L2 are the source of learner difficulties” (Munro, 2018, p. 269). On the other hand, Munro argues that other influences including learners’ language proficiency and L1 use in the classrooms determine whether a learner can be successful with a particular sound of English or not.

In Vietnamese contexts, Nguyen (2015) discovers popular challenges that Vietnamese learners of English have to face with when learning pronunciation. One of the explored difficulties is the problem with voiced and voiceless stops including the particular issue with /θ/ and /ð/. According to Nguyen (2015), speakers in Vietnam usually make a strongly voiceless stop /t/ instead of a voiceless fricative sound /θ/. Nguyen explains that the sound /t/ is vocalized from the letter *th* of their mother tongue which is heavily pronounce /t/.

Bui (2016) also finds out problems in pronouncing the sounds /θ/ and /ð/ of adult Vietnamese EFL learners. Bui determines that the consonant /θ/ is mainly replaced by /t’/ in Vietnamese language and the /ð/ sound is regularly mispronounced as /z/. According to Bui (2016), the factors affecting the participants’ pronunciation include the influence of Vietnamese, the learner’s lack of native input exposure as well as the English speaking environment, and the limited instructions on the sounds.

3. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to investigate how pronunciation of the *th* sounds /θ/ and /ð/ is difficult for EFL learners in Vietnam. The target population aimed to examine this language aspect are students from various English classes such as English A1, English B1 of Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry (HUPI) and students from TOEIC classes of HUPI’s Center of Foreign Languages. Their proficiency level ranges from A1 to B1 according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR).

To collect the data, students are randomly selected and asked to pronounce some particular English words containing /θ/ and /ð/ sounds which appear in their textbooks (LIFE

A1-A2, LIFE A2-B1, TOEIC Coursebook). Following that, their pronunciation results are thoroughly analyzed to find out the errors in their pronunciation of the above sounds. From the findings, their difficulties in pronouncing /θ/ and /ð/ sounds in English are investigated and explained.

4. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

It seems that the influence from Vietnamese pronunciation is one of the main causes of the difficulties in pronouncing the *th* sounds /θ/ and /ð/. In the language teaching and learning contexts in Vietnam, it is believed that the sound /ð/ is characterized by /d/ in Vietnamese pronunciation. In Vietnamese alphabet, it has the letter *đ* / *Đ* which is pronounced similarly as /d/ in English. For example, the Vietnamese word *đà* (if *đà* is a noun, it means *banyan tree* in English; if *đà* is an adjective, it means *many* or *much* in English) is pronounced like /dɑː/. As a result, many Vietnamese learners of English often pronounce /d/ for *th* sound /ð/ in English. For example, the English article ‘*the*’ is frequently pronounced as /də/ instead of the correct sound /ðə/.

Another reason is that the technique to pronounce /θ/ and /ð/ is completely different from the way to pronounce Vietnamese sounds. It is not easy for EFL learners in Vietnam to bring the tongue tip between the teeth when saying the sound of /ð/. Therefore, some of them find less difficult way to pronounce this sound is that they place the tongue tip touching the back of the teeth. That is why the *th* sounds /ð/ is sometimes pronounced like the sound of /d/ instead. /d/ is familiar with Vietnamese people and much easier to say. For instance, the word *weather* /'weðər/ may be said as /'wedər/ or /'wedə/ by Vietnamese students.

Whereas the voiced sound /ð/ is confused for /d/, the voiceless sound /θ/ is confused for /t^h/. Most of Vietnamese *th* words is not sounded /θ/ as in English but it is actually /t^h/. When pronouncing the sound /t^h/, a lot of air is released. In addition, the tongue does not need to come through the teeth. Because there is no equivalent of the sound of /t^h/ in English while it is existing in Vietnamese, learners of English in Vietnam is strongly influenced by the similar *th* sound /t^h/ of Vietnamese language when saying the *th* sound /θ/ in English. For instance, the word *think* /θɪŋk/ is incorrectly pronounced as /t^hɪŋk/ or /t^hɪnk/ by English learners in Vietnam. If they do not pronounce the final sound /k/ either, *think* may be erroneously pronounced as /t^hɪŋ/ or /t^hɪn/.

The language proficiency level is also a factor affecting the pronunciation learning and practicing of the students. The above pronunciation issue usually happens with students having low level of English language proficiency, especially elementary and pre-intermediate students. With upper-intermediate or higher proficiency level of students, the sounds of *th* (/θ/ and /ð/) are correctly pronounced when they say independent words or slowly speak a sentence containing the *th* sounds. Unfortunately, if the students pronounce the *th* words at a fast pace, the *th* sounds may be turned into the similar sound /t^h/ (instead of /θ/) or /d/ (instead of /ð/) in Vietnamese language. In order to correctly make two *th* consonant sounds, the tongue has to come through the teeth. Consequently, the reason for the erroneous sounds of *th* may be because there is not enough time for the speakers to move the tongue forward.

In order to effectively instruct learners how to properly pronounce the sound of /θ/, teachers should advise them to bring the tongue tip between the teeth. The tongue tip should be visible to other students. Because /θ/ sound is unvoiced, they need to make air blow through the mouth without biting the tongue tip. Moreover, they need to remain the lips without moving them down when pronouncing /θ/. We can illustrate this sound by holding a soft and thin piece of paper in front of the mouth. When pronouncing /θ/, the air passing through the mouth will make the piece of paper move forward. On the other hand, the sound of /ð/ is voiced. The technique to pronounce /ð/ is almost similar to the sound /θ/, except that this sound is made with the vocal cords. Again, we can use a soft and thin piece of paper in front of the mouth when pronouncing /ð/, but it will not move forward this time because /ð/ is a voiceless sound.

In addition, using minimal pairs in teaching pronunciation is also a good method to help students listen, distinguish and practice the different sounds. The minimal pairs should contain similar sounds which easily confuse the learners, for example /s/ and /θ/, /f/ and /θ/, /t/ and /θ/, /d/ and /ð/, /z/ and /ð/. Together with teaching minimal pairs, some sentences and conversations containing the sounds need to be provided to help students practice and apply in authentic communication situations. According to Tejada and Santos (2014), it is proved that teachers' instructions of pronunciation is necessary but not enough in learning English language. Increasing practice for the students is the main factor to improve and boost their pronunciation as well as their confidence in EFL speaking ability (Tejada & Santos, 2014).

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is noticed that Vietnamese learners of English frequently encounter problems when pronouncing the *th* sounds /θ/ and /ð/ in English. The factors causing the pronunciation difficulties vary including the influence of Vietnamese language, the tough way of using tongue and teeth to pronounce /θ/ and /ð/, and the low level of language proficiency of learners. Being aware of the students' difficulties in pronunciation can help the teachers develop their teaching English pronunciation as well as can help students improve their learning and practicing pronunciation. In order to effectively teach English pronunciation, teachers of English need to give comprehensive instructions of how to correctly pronounce the sounds, use minimal pairs with lots of examples, and provide a motivated environment for the students to learn and practice pronunciation.

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